

PRODUCTION AND EVALUATION OF INTRA-FILAMENT HYBRIDS

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1. Introduction

A hybrid composite may be defined as a material consisting of two or more types of reinforcements in a single or binary matrix. A general classification system for hybrid composites is presented in Fig. 1. The proposed classification also includes tufted/stitched, z-pinning and “z-axis” fibre reinforced composites. In these classes of composites, the fibres that reinforce or stitch the layers of the preform can be of a different composition or micro-structure to the primary reinforcing fibres. Since the z-axis composite is a new development, a photograph to indicate the density of the “vertical” fibres that can be achieved is presented in Fig. 2 (without the top-layer of the sandwich structure). Here, short-E-glass fibres have been aligned vertically (z-axis) and bonded to a 4-layer cross-ply carbon fibre composite.

Hybrid composites continue to attract significant attention because: (i) they can offer properties that cannot be attained by mono-fibre composites; (ii) relatively high-performance and expensive fibres can be hybridized with cheaper reinforcements including those derived from natural sources; (iii) a number of researchers have demonstrated that they can yield improved properties such as impact [1-4], tensile [5-8] and other relevant mechanical properties [9-10]; and (iv) a number of hypotheses have been proposed to account for the so-called “hybrid effect”.

Two definitions of the hybrid effect have been proposed previously. In the first case, the hybrid composite is considered to consist of two fibre types where their relative strains-to-failure are considerably different; they are designated as high and low-elongation fibres. The enhancement of the failure strain of the low-elongation fibres in the hybrid composite, when compared to that of the low-elongation mono-fibre composite, is attributed to the hybrid effect. In the second case, a positive or negative deviation from the rule-of-mixtures (RoM) is used as the presence/absence of the hybrid effect.

The following section has been summarised from reference [11]. Hayashi [12] reported that the first fracture stress and strain for a unidirectional carbon/glass hybrid was 37% and 45% higher respectively than that predicted by the RoM. Hayashi attributed this synergistic effect to the carbon fibres being surrounded by the glass fibres which had a higher failure strain. Kalnin [13] found that the failure mode in carbon/glass hybrids depended on their relative volume fractions. A catastrophic failure mode was observed when the volume fraction of carbon was high. He also reported that the initial fracture strain of the carbon fibres in the hybrid was greater than in the all-carbon fibre composite. Hancox and Wells [14] reported that the impact energy for a 50:50 carbon fibre: glass core sandwich structure was between 2.5-5 times higher when compared to the all-carbon composite with an equivalent fibre volume fraction. They reasoned that the glass fibre core could store higher strain energy. Bunsell and Harris [15] revisited the findings for Hayashi [12] and found that for the carbon/glass hybrid in question, the initial modulus was in agreement with the RoM up to the fracture of the carbon fibre in the hybrid; they also found that the failure strain of the carbon fibres in the hybrid at this point was greater than that of the failure strain of carbon fibres in the all-carbon fibre composite. Bunsell and Harris [15] attribute the hybrid effect in part to the residual compressive fabrication stress in the carbon fibres. Aveston and Sillwood [16] reported a 100% increase in the fibre strength for the carbon fibres in a carbon/glass hybrid composite. According to the model that was proposed by these authors, the low-elongation fibres have to be present as thin layers where their volume fraction is low, and distributed evenly throughout the matrix. They defined the failure strain as the strain at which the low-elongation fibres undergo multiple fractures with a defined crack spacing. They went on to speculate that the glass fibres may enhance the failure strain of the carbon fibres by inhibiting catastrophic crack propagation. Zweben [17] extended a statistical model previously developed by

Rosen and Zweben [18], to describe the tensile strength of unidirectional hybrid composites consisting of 2-dimensional arrays of alternating low and high-elongation fibres in a common matrix. Fukuda [19] progressed the analyses developed by Zweben and obtained good agreement with the experimental data published by other researchers. Unlike the failure sequence proposed by Zweben, Fukuda argued that when one low-elongation fibre fractures at its weakest point under applied load, the next failure is expected on the adjacent low-elongation fibre. Fukuda defined the hybrid effect as the enhancement of the initial failure strain of the low-elongation fibres. Manders and Bader [20] also adopted a statistical approach to model the strength of hybrid composites. They proposed two terms in their analysis: the hybrid ratio and the state of dispersion. The hybrid ratio was defined as the proportion of a specified fibre type to the total amount of fibre in the hybrid composite. Dispersion was defined as the reciprocal of the smallest repeat unit of the laminates. The hybrid effect was expressed as the percentage increase of the failure strain of the low-elongation fibres in the hybrid compared with that of the mono-fibre low-elongation composite. They reported that a greater hybrid effect was observed in a carbon/glass hybrid when the carbon fibres were dispersed finely and where their volume fraction was low. Interestingly, they also reported that in the mono-fibre carbon composites, the initial failure strain was a function of the thickness of the laminate; the thicker laminates failed at higher strains. They speculated that this may have been due to imperfect fibre alignment in the prepregs. Xing *et al.* [21] emphasised that the dynamic stress state should be considered instead of the static case during mechanical loading of hybrids. Harlow has published extensively on tensile behavior of intra-ply hybrids [22-24]. Pan and Postle [25] presented a detailed study to account for the factors that they considered to be responsible for observed deviations from RoM behavior in hybrids.

A common theme in a number of the above-mentioned papers is that the best utilisation of individual fibre properties seems to be obtained when two fibre types are dispersed uniformly and where the volume fraction of the low-elongation fibre is low. However, most of the published experimental research work has been concentrated on inter-ply hybrid composites, presumably because of the ease with which these can be manufactured.

Intra-ply woven hybrids are commercially available, but the fibre dispersion is at the fibre-bundle level.

This paper reports on the design and development of a rig to enable the production of intra-filament hybrids. The methodology is focused on spreading the filaments in bundles of carbon and glass fibres. The spread fibre bundles are then subjected to secondary manipulation to create intra-filament hybrid bundles. An added benefit of spreading the filament in a bundle is that it enhances the rate of through-thickness impregnation [26].

2. Design of fibre spreading rig

2.1 The original fibre spreading rig: The background theory [27] and the details of the mode of operation of the fibre rig [28] was presented previously where a fibre tow was spread by 250% when compared to as-received 2400 tex E-glass. In the current paper, a brief description is given where a simple modification of the fibre spreading rig enabled a tow to be spread by up to 800% for a glass fibre tow.

A photograph of the original fibre spreading rig is presented in Fig. 3 [28]. The rig consists of three motorised carrier hubs which were mounted in a Perspex chassis. Each of the carrier hubs consist of an acetal central drive shaft, which in turn drives a Perspex bearing housing (disc), positioned at each end of the shaft. The bearing housings have multiple recessed positions arranged around their circumference in which ball bearings were fitted to support a series of acetal rollers that could be fitted in any of the single or multiple positions as illustrated in Fig. 4. Each of the rotating carrier hub roller assemblies is driven independently by a 12-Volt DC direct-drive motor and gearbox.

The acetal rods (Direct Plastics, UK) with a diameter of 30 mm and a length of 300 mm were used. The diameter of the Perspex disc was 150 mm. The revolutions per minute (rpm) of the discs were measured using a digital photo tachometer (Model: RM-1501, RS Calibration). The larger-diameter roller positioned subsequent to the third rotating carrier hub assembly was meant to preserve the spreading achieved as the tow traversed towards the haul-off unit.

2.2 Modified fibre spreading rig

(i) *Spreading glass fibre tows:* The rig shown in Fig. 3 was modified to increase the degree of spreading that could be attained. Here, the tow was

fed into the pre-tensioning system with minimal tension; one of the acetal rollers mentioned previously was laid on top of the tow to prevent it twisting as it was hauled through the fibre spreading rig. The pre-tensioning system in this instance consisted of four aluminium rollers of 10 mm diameter where the glass tow was made to follow a serpentine trajectory. Three 30 mm acetal bars were positioned on top of the rollers to add further tension.

The tow was then directed over the first powered roller carrier hub. This set contained two horizontally opposed rollers and two horizontally opposed pins. Unlike the previous case, here a velvet-type brushing medium was attached to the pin with the nap orientated to brush the tow when driven in the anti-clockwise direction. The rotational speed was set at approximately two revolutions per second. The tow then encounters the second roller carrier hub, identical to the first but with the velvet nap in the opposite direction to enable clockwise direction at the same speed.

The third roller carrier hub contains two rollers, horizontally opposed and at their greatest distance. This produces a cam effect physically inducing an intermittent tension and relaxation within the tow; this action is termed “tension-release”. This is driven at approximately one revolution per second.

The tow then comes into light contact with a 100 mm diameter acetal pin followed by a “floating” guide which controls the width of the spread tow. The spread tow is then wound onto a haul-off bobbin where a layer of tissue paper is co-wound beneath the tow to resist entanglement and to allow easier un-winding.

(ii) *Spreading carbon fibre tows:* The modified fibre spreading rig was found to be suitable for E-glass fibres but it was not appropriate for carbon fibres as significant segmentation and fibre damage was observed at the modified contact-points. A simple technique for enhancing the spreading of the carbon fibre tows was stumbled upon accidentally. At the end of each experimental session on the fibre spreading rig, a domestic vacuum cleaner is used to clean the workbench. In this occasion, a length of carbon fibre tow between the creel and the rig was sucked in accidentally; whilst removing this section from the nozzle of the vacuum cleaner, it was observed that the tow spreads laterally as it is permitted to be sucked in; tensioning the fibre

resulted in the width of the tow decreasing from its spread state. The authors were aware of a patent by Kawabe *et al.* [29] who used compressed air to induce lateral spreading of the fibres. This technique was deemed unsuitable by the current authors because of the potential for generating airborne carbon dust which is a significant risk for electrical equipment. However, a careful scrutiny of this patent did indicate that in addition to compressed air (above the tow), a suction device is used below the tow.

In the current study, a suction device was built and positioned in close proximity to the haul-off mandrel (item-vii in Fig. 3). The original fibre spreading rig, with the tension-release mechanism was used to create and release the tension. At the point where the tension is released in the fibre spreading rig, a portion of the tow is drawn into the suction device; the rotating haul-off spool capture a proportion of the tow in its spread state.

3 Experimental

3.1 Details of fibres

The E-glass fibres used in this study were 2400 tex from two suppliers. These have been coded as tow type-G1 and tow type-G2. Tow type-G1 had approximately 4000 filaments with an average filament diameter of $17 \pm 2 \mu\text{m}$. Tow type-G2 had a filament count of 2400 with an average filament diameter of $22 \pm \mu\text{m}$.

The carbon fibres tows used in the experiments reported here were also from two suppliers and have been coded as type-C1 (24K) and type-C2 (6K).

3.2 Fibre spreading with original rig

With reference to Fig. 3, the following parameters were considered to have an influence on the extent of fibre spreading. (i) The number of rollers or pins on each of the carrier hub. (ii) The diameter of rollers or pins present on each of the carrier hub. (iii) The rotational velocity and the direction of rotation of the carrier hub. (iv) The haul-off speed of the fibre tows. (v) The magnitude of the friction experienced by the fibre tow. (vi) The tension on the fibre tow. (vii) The degree of twists in the fibre tow. (viii) The binder-content on the fibre tow and the tex of the tow.

The design and optimisation of the automated fibre spreading rig was reported by the authors previously [27]. Minitab[®] software was used to generate the

L18 experimental matrix (shown in Table 2) using the factors and their levels enlisted in Table 1. The detail of the six disk configurations (factor A) is shown in Fig. 4. The response parameters selected for the optimisation were: (i) minimum fibre damage and segmentation (observed visually); and (ii) width of the fibre tow after spreading (measured at carrier hub assembly-3, see Fig. 3). Each experiment was repeated ten times to obtain the average values for the degree of fibre spreading.

Type-G1 glass and type-C1 carbon fibres were used in the experiments reported in this section.

3.3 Fibre spreading with modified rig

Fibre spreading experiments with modified rig were carried out according to the method described in Section 2.2. Type-G2 glass and type-C2 carbon fibre tows were used in these experiments.

3.4 Hybridisation

At the time of writing, a number of techniques were being investigated to enable the pre-spread glass and carbon fibres to be inter-laced to create intimately hybridised glass and carbon filaments. In this preliminary work reported here, and to demonstrate the proof-of-principle, type-G2 glass and type-C2 carbon tows were spread individually to approximately 800% and wound on to a bobbin. Sections of the spread tows were then unwound and any segmentation was coaxed back into position manually using a carbon or glass fibre brush. The spread tows were then stacked and the surface was brushed lightly with the appropriate brush (depending on the fibre type that was on the top). It is anticipated that this manual process will be replaced in the future by a semi-automated process.

3.5 Tensile testing

The as-received and spread E-glass fibres were end-tabbed prior to tensile testing. Aluminium end-tabs of dimension 60 mm × 25 mm × 1.5 mm were fabricated and the leading-edge of the end-tab was abraded using 240 grit abrasive paper to remove any burrs. The end-tabs were then degreased using acetone in an ultrasonic bath for 10 minutes. After degreasing, the end-tabs were dried in an air-circulating oven at 50 °C for 20 minutes. A thin coating of Scotch-Weld adhesive (9323-2 3M UK) was applied to the bonding surfaces to prevent any unintentional damage to the filaments that come into direct contact with the metal end-tab. Once this thin layer was cured, the glass fibre tows were end-tabbed using a custom-designed end-tab jig where

the spatial orientation of the tow and the end-tab was maintained during the room-temperature curing of the above-mentioned resin. Due care and attention was given to ensure that the tow was impregnated fully within the end-tab. Care was also taken not to alter the spatial architecture of the filaments but this was not possible in every case because the width and the degree of segmentation in the as-received tow were variable in some cases. Light-tension was applied to each tow during end-tabbing. The gauge lengths (length of the tow between the end-tabs) used in this study were 50, 80, 100, 150 and 200 mm.

It is acknowledged that the length of the end-tabs used here meant that 10 mm protruded from the grips of the mechanical test machine. This was necessary for the following reasons: (i) it provided a means to attach a pair of piezo-electric transducers in a repeatable manner at each end; (ii) it meant that it was not necessary to attach the transducers on the fibre tow; and (iii) it negated the need to apply a coupling medium between the surfaces of the transducer and the fibre tow to ensure the required level of coupling. It is known that lubricating the tows can influence the fracture behavior.

The end-tabbed tows were tensile tested to failure on an Instron 5566 mechanical test machine at a cross-head displacement rate of 0.1 mm/minute. The tensile tests were carried out at room temperature (20 ± 2 °C).

3.6 Acoustic emission

A pair of piezo-electric transducers (Wideband, PAC, UK) was surface-mounted on the end-tab using paraffin wax as the coupling medium. An adhesive tape was used to secure the transducers on the surface of the end-tabs. The operating frequency range of the transducer was 100-900 kHz. The signals from the piezo-electric transducers were amplified by 40 dB using a pre-amplifier (General purpose low-noise industry standard with plug-in filter provisions, 20/40/60 dB switchable gain, single-ended or differential). Two parametric channels from the data acquisition systems were connected to the Instron machine for acquiring the load and the displacement data. The threshold for the acoustic emission data acquisition was set at 35 dB. The following data acquisition settings were adopted: (i) peak definition time = 50 µs; (ii) hit definition time = 100 µs; and (iii) hit lock-out time = 100 µs. The front-end filter setting for the signal duration was 250 µs and the maximum hit duration

was 20 ms. Simulated AE events were generated using pencil lead breaks to ascertain the efficiency of the coupling between the aluminium/sample interfaces and to evaluate the wave speed.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Fibre spreading with original rig

A summary of the fibre widths obtained for both carbon (type-C1) and E-glass (type-G1) tows via the Taguchi-based analysis is presented in Fig. 5. The fibres in this study were drawn from the outside of the creel. The results shown in Fig. 5 were used to generate the “main effect plots” based on the signal-to-noise ratios (S/N) for the factors and levels stated in Table 1. Here the objective of the experiments was to enhance the widths of the tows, hence S/N were chosen to be “larger-the-better”. The main effect plots for carbon and E-glass tows are shown in Figs. 6 and 7 respectively.

On inspecting Figs. 6 and 7 it was established that the optimum combinations of parameters to attain maximum fibre spreading were A2/B3/C1/D3 and A3/B3/C1/D3 for carbon and E-glass tows respectively. It was concluded via analysis of variance (ANOVA) that all the factors chosen in this study were statistically significant. Furthermore, it can be seen for carbon fibre tows (Fig. 6) the S/N values for A2 and A3 are very close. As the combination A3/B3/C1/D3 is present in the experimental matrix presented in Table 2 (experiment 9). This was selected to obtain the spread carbon and E-glass tows which were used in the hybridisation experiments reported in the next section.

4.2 Fibre spreading with modified rig

Fig. 8 shows the output from a series of preliminary experiments to demonstrate that the degree of spreading of an E-glass tow can be controlled when using the modified fibre spreading rig. With reference to Fig. 8, the terms “controlled” fibre width represents the situations where the width of the spread tow does not exhibit any segmentation or gaps. Likewise, “uncontrolled” means that there is some segmentation in the spread fibre tow. In summary, the modified fibre spreading rig enables the overall width of the tow to be controlled. The preliminary results obtained suggests that the segmentation observed when the degree of spreading is greater than 800% may not be an issue because it can be rectified as it is wound on to the bobbin or as part of the hybridisation process.

Visual observations did not indicate the presence of any significant fibre fractures in the spread carbon and glass fibre tows that were obtained using the modified fibre spreading rig. However, it is acknowledged that techniques will need to be developed to assess the degree of damage (if any) that is caused as a consequence of spreading.

Fig. 9 shows the relative widths for the as-received type-G1, type-G2, type-C1 and type-C2 tows. A fair degree of variation was observed in the widths of the as-received tows. In the case of the glass fibres, it was observed that the binder content was not consistent. These issues had an influence on the relative uniformity of the spread tows. Figs. 10 (a and b) illustrate the point that the degree of fibre spreading can now be controlled by adjusting the various operation parameters of the modified fibre spreading rig.

The mode of operation of the original fibre spreading rig in conjunction with the suction-based device is illustrated in Figs. 11 (a-f). The function of the fibre spreading rig in this instance was to: (i) breakup the binder in the type-C2 carbon fibre tow; and (ii) to apply a cyclical tension on/off sequence to the tow as it is unwound from the creel and wound on to the fibre haul-off unit. The vacuum device was positioned over the mandrel on the fibre haul-off unit. The initial image shows the as-received or tension state with the subsequent images showing the changes in relative widths of the tow as it is drawn towards the vacuum port when the tension is released. As the tension is reapplied by the rotating carrier hub, the spread width of the tow returns to its approximate as-received dimension. Positioning the vacuum device in close proximity to the haul-off mandrel enables a portion of the spread tow to be captured. The so-called tension-release process is cyclical. Significant improvements can be made to capture the tow when it is at its maximum spread configuration, and this will be the subject of a subsequent publication.

4.3 Hybridisation

Figs. 12 (a and b) show the principle of hybridization that will be developed. Fig. 12 (a) shows a spread type-G2 tow resting over a spread type-C2 carbon tow. It is readily apparent that there is significant segmentation in the glass tows but this is in part due to the variability in the architecture of the as-received tow. Optimisation of the modified fibre spreading rig is likely to enable the production of near-mono-layers of glass fibre filaments; this

will obviously make it relatively straightforward to hybridise the spread tow with two or more fibre types. As indicated previously, the degree of segmentation observed in Fig. 12 (a) may not be an issue as the gaps between the filaments can be reduced by secondary manipulation. Fig. 12 (b) shows a spread type-C2 carbon resting on a spread type-G2 tow. The spread tow was brushed manually (using a short stub of the as-received carbon tow) to induce it to fall into the interstitial spaces in the glass tow. A section of this “hybridised” material was coated with a photo-curable resin and cured. Fig. 13 (a and b) show optical micrographs to illustrate the dispersion that has been achieved in the preliminary trial to hybridise the spread glass and carbon tows manually. This technique will be progressed whereby a semi-automatic methodology for hybridizing the spread tows will be developed.

4.4 Tensile testing and acoustic emission

The tensile strengths of the as-received and spread fibres for five different gauge lengths are shown in Fig. 14. A decrease in the strength was observed with an increase in the gauge length. Also it was observed that spread fibres showed improved tensile strength as compared to the as-received fibres. The dependence of tensile strength on the gauge length may be attributed to the number of flaws on the surface of the filaments which may initiate the breakage. Also the stress distribution capability of the fibres may have increased at shorter gauge lengths. It was also observed that the spread fibres showed an improved tensile strength when compared to the as-received fibres. The dependence of tensile strength on the gauge length is well known and the data presented in Fig. 14 agrees with the data presented by other researchers. The observed marginal improvement in the tow tensile strength for the spread type-G1 fibres needs further research. However, given the fact that thirty samples were tested at each of the specified gauge lengths, there is some confidence in the observed trend. It is speculated that this observed improvement in the tensile strength of the tow may be attributed to one or more of the following: (i) there are intrinsic twists in the tows and these originate from the manufacturing process of the E-glass rovings [28]; (ii) in situations where there is crimping of the tow within the creel, the relative orientation of the individual filaments is not strictly unidirectional; and (iii) with some fibre types, the binder content on the tows was “clumpy”. These factors can have an influence on how the individual filaments in the tow are loaded during tensile testing. Furthermore, in

the case of the spread tows, a higher proportion of the filaments are unidirectional because some of the meandering of the filaments is straightened by the mode of spreading. Thus, it is likely that a greater number of the filaments are loaded uniformly during the tensile test. Conversely, in the case of the as-received tow, not only is the binder intimately associated with the filaments, the end-tapping resin (with a relatively high viscosity in the current case) has to be massaged into the tow as well. Finally, it is likely that the gripping of a relatively flat profile in the mechanical test machine (as in the case of the spread tow), the loading of the individual filaments may be more uniform when compared with an as-received tow.

The influences of fibre spreading and the gauge length were studied by using a two-factor factorial design [30]. From the analysis of variance, it is concluded that fibre spreading and the gauge length influence significantly the tensile behavior of the tows. However, the major contribution towards the results was from the gauge length (54.45 %).

The tensile properties of the fibre tow were further investigated by implementing the Weibull distribution, given by:

$$S(\sigma) = \exp\left[-\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_o}\right)^m\right] \quad (1)$$

where, σ is the applied load, $S(\sigma)$ is the applied load probability of survival, σ_o is a scale factor that corresponds to the severity of flaws, and m is the shape factor that relates to the distribution of flaws within the fibre. Equation 1 is then elaborated, as follows:

$$\ln(-\ln(S)) = m\ln(\sigma) - m\ln(\sigma_o) \quad (2)$$

A summary of the Weibull analysis on type-G1 fibre tows as a function of gauge length and fibre spreading is shown in Table 4. The representative acoustic emission data for one as-received E-glass tow is shown in Fig. 15.

The Weibull diagram and corresponding fibre survival probability graph for E-glass fibres at two gauge lengths (50 mm and 200 mm) are shown in Figs. 16 and 17 respectively. It can be seen from these Figures that the fibres with a shorter gauge length (50 mm) can withstand higher loads prior to fracture.

5 Conclusions

A custom-designed rig was used to spread the individual filaments in as-received carbon and glass

fibre tows. The maximum degree of fibre spreading achieved to-date, using the rig, for carbon and glass fibres were 300 % and 250 % respectively.

The rig was modified to improve the spreading of the fibre tows of glass and carbon. In the case of the glass fibres, felt-type brushes were introduced to the roller carrier assembly. With reference to carbon, the fibre spreading rig was used in its original configuration but a vacuum device was introduced and positioned over the haul-off unit. In both cases, the applying and releasing the tension on the tows, aided the fibre spreading process. The maximum degree of fibre spreading achieved to-date, after modifications, for carbon and glass tows was >800 % and >1000% respectively. These pre-spread tows were subjected to secondary manual-manipulation to demonstrate a novel class of intra-filament hybrids.

Tensile testing was performed on as-received and spread Type-G1 E-glass fibre tows to study the effect of gauge length and fibre spreading on tensile properties. It was shown via ANOVA and Weibull analysis that tensile strength decreases as the gauge length was increased for the as-received and spread fibres. It was also observed that spreading the filaments in a tow marginally increased the tensile strength.

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Fig. 1 Schematic illustration of a classification system for conventional and hybrid composites. Details as follows: (a) conventional mono-fibre; (b) inter-ply hybrid where the open and filled circles represent two different fibre types (carbon/glass, carbon/aramid, high-modulus/high-strength carbon, etc); (c) intra-ply (intra-filament); (d) intra-ply (tow hybrids or co-mingled); (e) Inter-ply reinforced hybrid (the reinforcement can be particulates or short-fibres); (f) inter-leaved (similar matrix or a resin system with a significantly higher toughness); (g) skin/core hybrid; (h) fibre skin, non-fibre core hybrid; (i) tufted, z-pinned and stitched; and (j) z-axis.

Fig. 2 Photograph of a z-axis composites (the top-layer of the sandwich structure is not present).

Fig. 3 Photograph of the fibre spreading rig. (i) input fibre, (ii) pre-tensioning system, (iii) first roller carrier hub, (iv) second roller carrier hub, (v) third roller carrier hub, (vi) exit roller, (vii) mandrel, (viii) haul-off motor.

Fig. 4 Details of the roller-disk configurations. Here the solid circle represents the central shaft of the rotating roller-disk assembly and the unfilled circle represents the acetel rollers [28].

Fig. 5 Summaries of the widths of the carbon and E-glass tows for eighteen experiments enlisted in Table 2. Each bar in the histogram represents an average of 10 individual samples. AR refers to as-received widths of the type-G1 and type-C1 glass and carbon fibre tows. (*AR – As-received tow)

Table 1 Factors and levels selected in the experimental matrix.

Factors	Factor description	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5	Level 6
A	Configuration	1	2	3	4	5	6
B	Pre-tension (N)	2	6	10	-	-	-
C	Pull speed (m/min)	1	3	5	-	-	-
D	Disk rotation (rpm)	25	50	100	-	-	-

* See Fig. 4 for the details of each of the rotating roller-disk configurations.

Table 2 Taguchi-based experimental matrix for the L₁₈ orthogonal array.

Factors	Experiment number																	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
A	1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	3	4	4	4	5	5	5	6	6	6
B	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
C	1	2	3	1	2	3	2	3	1	3	1	2	2	3	1	3	1	2
D	1	2	3	2	3	1	1	2	3	3	1	2	3	1	2	2	3	1

Fig. 6 Main effect plots for signal-to-noise ratio for the experiments performed with type-C1 carbon fibre tows.

Fig. 7 Main effect plots for signal-to-noise ratio for the experiments performed with type-G1 E-glass fibre tows.

Fig. 8 Tow widths for the as-received and spread type-G2 E-glass demonstrating that the spreading obtained using the modified spreading rig can be controlled as desired.

Fig. 9 Photograph showing the relative as-received widths of the glass and carbon fibres used in this study.

Figs. 10 (a and b) Photographs of the spread type-G2 E-glass illustrating the fact that the degree of spreading can be controlled when using the modified fibre spreading rig.

Figs. 11 (a-f) Sequential images showing the relative widths of an as-received type-C2 carbon fibre tow (image (a)) as it is subjected to the suction of a vacuum; one end of the fibre is attached to the haul-off bobbin/mandrel whilst the other is fed from the creel via the fibre spreading rig.

Figs. 12 (a and b): (a) Photograph showing a type-G2 and type-C2 carbon fibres that have been spread to a “maximum” value on the modified fibre spreading rig. The glass tow was spread using the modified fibre spreading rig. Note the segmentation in the spread glass tow. The carbon tow was spread using the original fibre spreading rig and the vacuum suction device; and (b) Photograph showing the aftermath of brushing (manually) a spread carbon tow that is resting on a spread glass tow.

Figs. 13 (a and b) Micrographs showing the degree of dispersion that was achieved in the preliminary experiments where the spread glass and carbon fibre tows were laid on top of each other and manipulated manually. In Fig. 13 a, the dark border represents the shrinkage of the photo-curable resin from the potting resin. The vertical striations observed in Fig. 13 (b) may be attributed to shrinkage of the photo-curable resin. It is emphasised that these are micrographs from preliminary experiments.

Table 3. Analysis of variance for maximum tensile strength of fibre tow (type-G1)

Source of variation	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Mean square	F _o	P-value	Percentage contribution
Gauge length	2142830.971	4	535707.7	104.5292	less than 0.0001	54.45
Spreading	211364.2979	1	211364.3	41.24216	less than 0.0001	5.29
Interaction	56828.48557	4	14207.12	2.772144	0.0275	0.93
Error	1486237.614	290	5124.957			
Total	3897261.368	299				

Table 4. Summary of Weibull analysis on type-G1 fibre tow as function of gauge length and fibre spreading

	Gauge Length									
	50 mm		80 mm		100 mm		150 mm		200 mm	
	m	σ_o , cN/tex	m	σ_o , cN/tex	m	σ_o , cN/tex	m	σ_o , cN/tex	m	σ_o , cN/tex
As-received	21.05	46.94	28.95	44.86	9.41	42.01	14.43	38.96	16.34	38.28
Spread	14.96	51.15	24.89	45.23	16.62	44.08	15.78	40.76	21.87	40.56

Figure 14 Comparison of the maximum tensile load of as-received and spread type-G1 E-glass tows as a function of gauge length.

Fig. 15 Acoustic emission data for as-received type-G1 E-glass tow.

Fig. 16 Plot of $\ln(-\ln(S(\sigma)))$ against $\ln(\sigma)$; as-received type-G1 fibre tows.

Fig. 17 Survival probability of as received and spread type-G1 fibre tows with gauge length of 100 mm.